

Spectroscopic Studies of some Organic Compounds. Part-I. Aprotic Solvent Effects on Electronic Absorption Spectra of 2-[*p*-(4-Methylpiperidino)phenyl]cinchoninic Acid

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Solvent as a medium for chemical and physical processes has always played a very important role in chemistry. Solvent effects on $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic spectral transitions are well described by the solvatochromic equation of general form^{1,2},

$$XYZ = XYZ_0 + s(\pi^* + d\delta) + a\alpha + b\beta \quad (1)$$

where π^* -scale of dipolarity-polarisability describes the ability of solvent to stabilise a solute charge or dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect; α -scale of hydrogen bond donor (HBD) acidities; measure the solvent ability to share a proton in a solvent to solute hydrogen bond; β -scale of hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA) basicities; measure the solvent ability to share a proton from an hydrogen bond donor solute; δ -polarisability correction term equal to (0.0) for nonchlorinated aliphatic solvent, (0.5) for polychlorinated aliphatic and (1.0) for aromatic solvents; s , d , a and b represent the responses of XYZ to the solvent polarity-polarisability and hydrogen bonding properties; XYZ terms in equation (1) may be the logarithm constant, the position or intensity of maximal absorption in spectrum^{3,4}. Correlation of these type has been the subject of extensive study.

The present work is concerned with the application of the solvatochromic equation (1) to resolve solvent effect on the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transitions of 2-[*p*-(4-methylpiperidino)phenyl]cinchoninic acid.

Results and Discussion

The acid was synthesised by Pfitzinger reaction⁵ by the condensation of isatin with 4-methylpiperidinoacetophenone in basic medium (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Such ketones involved in the synthesis have demonstrated the formation of only one major product of the acid in good yield. Although the utilisation of unsymmetrical ketones in Pfitzinger reaction has been widely investigated⁶, it seems more probable that under basic condition and the steric factors due to the presence of bulky group, the *anti*-conformer of type shown⁶, is the more predominant one which leads to the corresponding acid formation

The structural assignment of 2 was achieved by spectral and physical data. This compound showed a very bright intense colour which changes in solvents as well as in acidic and basic media. This phenomenon encouraged us to study its behaviour in the uv spectra, thus the uv spectra in sixteen aprotic solvents were measured. The region of the absorption could be attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. It was found that solvatochromic shifts were towards the red with increasing solvent polarity (negative s value)⁴, which suggests that uv bands show bathochromic shifts with increasing solvent polarity and follow the π^* pattern of behaviour¹. The data are listed in Table 1 together with the solvent parameters. Electronic spectral transitions from a ground state (I) to an excited state (II) are given. The charge is generated in the electronic excited state and the structures are stabilised by solvent polarity in accord with simple electrostatic theory. Hence the polar solvent facilitates excitation and results in a bathochromic shift as compared to the non-polar solvent.

A linear plot is obtained by using solvatochromic equation by the method of multiple parameter least-square correlation (multiple linear regression analysis), where wave number (ν) is plotted against polarity-polarisability term (π^*). A straight line is obtained of correlation coefficient

(0.92) and intercept (38.376) and slope (-6.343) (equation 2),

$$(10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}) \nu_{\text{max}} = 38.376 - 6.639 (\pi^* + 0.473 \delta) \pm 0.756 \quad (2)$$

$$n = 16 \quad r = 0.920.$$

Then the same procedure is followed by introducing β and α in multiregression analysis. It was found that the introduction of β and α in multiregression analysis does not improve the correlation coefficient. Also from examining the ratio s/b (6.3) and s/a (6.6) (equations 3 and 4),

$$(10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}) \nu_{\text{max}} = 38.376 - 6.343 (\pi^* + 0.473 \delta) \pm 0.756 - 0.996 \beta \pm 0.839 \quad (3)$$

$$n = 16 \quad r = 0.920.$$

Fig. 1 shows plot of $\nu_{\text{max-obs.}}$ vs $\nu_{\text{max, cal.}}$ according to equation (4),

$$(10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}) \nu_{\text{max}} = 38.385 - 6.257 (\pi^* + 0.473 \delta) \pm 0.489 - 1.131 \beta \pm 0.980 - 0.945 \alpha \pm 0.582 \quad (4)$$

$$n = 16 \quad r = 0.910.$$

d -Value (0.473) in equation (2) is calculated using standard equation reported previously¹. The positive sign of d means that the polarity correction term reinforces the π^* dipolarity-polarisability effect of the solvent.

TABLE I—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF 2-[p-(4-METHYL-PIPERIDINO)PHENYL]CINCHONINIC ACID IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS AND SOLVENTS PARAMETERS USED FOR MULTIPLE LINEAR CORRELATION

Solvent	ν_{max} $\times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	π^*	β	α
n-Hexane	39.21	-0.08	0.0	0.0
c-Hexane	38.75	0.0	0.0	0.0
Benzene	33.55	0.59	0.10	0.0
Toluene	34.48	0.54	0.11	0.0
Chlorobenzene	34.12	0.71	0.07	0.0
Bromobenzene	33.89	0.79	0.06	0.0
Carbontetrachloride	36.50	0.29	0.0	0.0
Chloroform	33.27	0.76	0.0	0.38
Dioxane	34.50	0.55	0.37	0.0
Diethylether	36.74	0.29	0.47	0.0
Tetrahydrofuran	33.33	0.58	0.55	0.0
Tetrahydrofuran	35.57	0.51	0.54	0.0
Ethylacetate	32.89	0.55	0.45	0.0
Acetone	32.50	0.71	0.37	0.0
Dimethylformamide	32.15	0.88	0.69	0.0
Dimethylsulphoxide	32.25	1.00	0.76	0.0

Negative sign of (s) in equations (2, 3, 4) indicates the inverse proportion between polarity-polarisability term of the solvent and wavenumber (ν), i.e. direct proportion with λ (bathochromic shift) means greater stabilisation of the excited state (II) through the solvent to a larger extent than ground state (I), hence reduced energy is required in the excitation of π -electron.

Fig. 1. Plot of ν_{max} observed vs ν_{max} predicted according to equation (4).

Negative sign of (a) and (b) means inverse proportion of acidity and basicity term and ν , direct proportion with λ , i.e. the solvent stabilises the excited state (II).

Experimental

¹H nmr spectra (deuteriopyridine) were recorded on a Bruker 60 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard, infrared spectra on a Pye-Unicam SP-2000 spectrophotometer and uv spectra on a Pye-Unicam SP-800 spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined on a Kofler hot-plate and are uncorrected.

The solvents used in the spectroscopic measurements were of spectroscopic grade whenever

possible. Commercial solvents were purified by standard method⁷. All solvents (Table 1) were distilled and the middle fraction was used. All uv spectral measurements were carried out at $\sim 20^\circ$ using $5 \times 10^{-5} M$ concentration of the corresponding compound. The analyses of results and solvatochromic equation were carried out by a Hyundai computer.

Compound (1): A mixture of *p*-fluoroacetophenone (0.094 mol) and the amine (0.282 mol) in dimethylformamide (45 ml) was stirred at 80° . The tertiary amine was precipitated by the addition of water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 87° .

Compound (2): A mixture of **1** (0.2 mol), isatin (0.1 mol) and potassium hydroxide (0.3 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed overnight. After the removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, water was added, and the impurities were removed by ether extraction. The aqueous layer was acidified

with acetic acid and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol-water, (72%), m.p. $218-20^\circ$; δ (deuteropyridine) 1.0 (3H, m, CH₃), 1.45-1.65 (5H, m, (CH₂)₂CH), 1.90 (2H, m, α -H_{ax}), 3.0 (2H, m, α -H_{eq}), 7.12-7.45 (4H, dd, ArH), 7.85-8.1 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.45 (1H, s, ArH); ν_{\max} 1700 (C=O), 1600 (C=C) and 3000 (OH, acid) cm^{-1} .

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